

STUDY TO IDENTIFY THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RECRUITMENT, SELECTION TOWARDS EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

V. T. Shailashri* & Dr. Surekha Shenoy**

* Research Scholar, Rayalaseema University, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh

** Professor, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka

Abstract

Every organization necessitates personnel planning as one of the most vital activities. Human Resource Planning is, by far, an essential ingredient for the success of any organization in the long run. There are a number of techniques that need to be followed by every organization that guarantees that it possesses the right number and type of people, at the right time and right place, so as to enable the organization to achieve its planned objectives. This paper is an attempt to identify a relationship between recruitment and selection in the process of engaging employees in the organization. A primary survey is conducted at Mathrubhumi Printing & Publishing Co.Ltd to establish this relationship. A sample study is conducted to determine the relationship between employee engagement and recruitment /selection. Recruitment function in the organization plays a pivotal role. Selection in the organization is a time consuming activity and care should be taken to see that the right kind of people are hired in the organization

Index Terms: Recruitment, Selection, Employee Engagement, Relationship & Primary Research

1. Introduction:

Recruitment is the process of attempting to locate and encourage potential applicants to apply for existing or anticipated job openings. In simple terms, Recruitment strategies attempt to create a pool of approximately qualified, skilled and experienced people so that, selection strategies and decision can be effective. *In short, recruitment is about sourcing the right people at the right time in the right place and at the right price.*

Attracting and retaining the right people is the cornerstone of an organization's success. The key to successful recruitment is to strengthen organization's relationship with both the current and potential workforce. Rather than maintaining temporary relationship with those who could fill one particular vacant position, the focus should be to keep long-term relationship with people who have the potential to work for the organization at some stage.

Recruitment forms first contact that a company makes with potential employees. It is through recruitment that many individual will come to know a company, and eventually decide whether they wish to work for it. A well planned and well managed recruiting effort will result in high quality applicants, whereas, a haphazard and piecemeal effort will result in mediocre ones. High quality employees cannot be selected when better candidates do not know of job openings, are not interested in working for the company, and do not apply. The recruitment process should inform qualified individuals about employment opportunities, create a positive image of the company, provide enough information of the jobs so that applicants can make comparisons with their qualifications and interests, and generate enthusiasm among the best candidates so that they will apply for the vacant positions.

Recruitment lends itself as a potential source of competitive advantage to a firm. An effective approach to recruitment can help a company successfully compete for limited human resources. The firm must choose a recruiting approach that produces the best pool of candidates quickly and cost effectively. A recruiting program helps the firm in at least four ways:

- ✓ Attract highly qualified and competent people.
- ✓ Ensure that the selected candidates stay longer with the company.
- ✓ Make sure that there is match between cost and benefit.
- ✓ Help the firm create more culturally diverse work-force.

The negative consequence of a poor recruitment process speaks volumes about its role in an organization. The failure to generate an adequate number of reasonably qualified applicants can prove costly in several ways. It can greatly complicate the selection process and may result in lowering of selection standards. Furthermore, when recruitment fails to meet organizational needs for talent, a typical response is to raise entry – level pay scales. This can distort traditional wage and salary relationships in the organization, resulting in unavoidable consequences. Thus the effectiveness of the recruitment process can play a major role in determining the resources that must be expended on other HR activities and their ultimate success.

The role of selection in an organization's effectiveness is crucial for at least, two reasons. First, *work performance* depends on individuals. The best way to improve performance is to hire people who have the competence and willingness to work. Arguing from employee's viewpoint, poor or inappropriate choice can be demoralizing to the individual concerned and de-motivating to the rest of the workforce. Effective selection, therefore, assumes greater relevance.

Second, *cost* incurred in recruiting and hiring personnel speaks volumes about the role of selection.

According to Korsten (2003) and Jones et al. (2006), Human Resource Management theories emphasize on techniques of recruitment and selection and outline the benefits of interviews, assessment and psychometric examinations as employee selection process. They further stated that recruitment process may be internal or external or may also be conducted online. Typically, this process is based on the levels of recruitment policies, job postings and details, advertising, job application and interviewing process, assessment, decision making, formal selection and training (Korsten 2003).

Jones et al. (2006) suggested that examples of recruitment policies in the healthcare, business or industrial sector may offer insights into the processes involved in establishing recruitment policies and defining managerial objectives.

Price (2007), in his work *Human Resource Management in a Business Context*, formally defines recruitment and selection as the process of retrieving and attracting able applications for the purpose of employment. He states that the process of recruitment is not a simple selection process, while it needs management decision making and broad planning in order to appoint the most appropriate manpower. Their existing competition among business enterprises for recruiting the most potential workers in on the pathway towards creating innovations, with management decision making and employers attempting to hire only the best applicants who would be the best fit for the corporate culture and ethics specific to the company (Price 2007). This would reflect the fact that the management would particularly shortlist able candidates who are well equipped with the requirements of the position they are applying for, including team work. Since possessing qualities of being a team player would be

essential in any management position (Price 2007). Hiltrop (1996) was successful in demonstrating the relationship between the HRM practices, HRM-organizational strategies as well as organizational performance. He conducted his research on HR manager and company officials of 319 companies in Europe regarding HR practices and policies of their respective companies and discovered that employment security, training and development programs, recruitment and selection, teamwork, employee participation, and lastly, personnel planning are the most essential practices (Hiltrop 1999). As a matter of fact, the primary role of HR is to develop, control, manage, incite, and achieve the commitment of the employees. The findings of Hiltrop's (1996) work also showed that selectively hiring has a positive impact on organizational performance, and in turn provides a substantial practical insight for executives and officials involved. Furthermore, staffing and selection remains to be an area of substantial interest. With recruitment and selection techniques for efficient hiring decisions, high performing companies are most likely to spend more time in giving training particularly on communication and team-work skills (Hiltrop 1999). Moreover the finding that there is a positive connection existing between firm performances and training is coherent with the human capital standpoint. Hence, Hiltrop (1996) suggests the managers need to develop HR practices that are more focused on training in order to achieve competitive benefits.

2. Company Profile:

Kerala is a state with a high literacy rate, which implies most of the people of Kerala know at least to read their mother tongue. This provides the newspaper industry, a good market in Kerala. This almost might be the reason that many new players are coming to this industry. Another reason for this emergency of the new players is that Kerala is known to be a Consumer State; it has got a sizeable market for many products. So the competition between the newspapers in Kerala is very high. The things which actually contribute the image of the newspaper are its reputation, new coverage or edibility, reach and quality.

Based in the northern Kerala town of Kozhikode, Mathrubhumi was founded in 1922 in the aftermath of Mahatma Gandhi's non-cooperation movement as a public limited company. This status makes it rare among newspapers, which tend to be closely held private companies owned by a single family

Mathrubhumi has a dedicated team of persons. There are about 2500 personnel in the organization. The Deputy General Manager, HRD, is the head of Human Resources Planning, Selection, Training and Development, Employee Health and Safety, Welfare Activities, Wage and Salary Administration, Maintain Good Labor and Procedures, Personnel Research and Performance Appraisal etc.

Products of Mathrubhumi:

Balabhumi (Children's Publication): Balabhumi was launched in the year 1996. It is a comprehensive Children's magazine. With comics, cartoons, series, stories, and proverbs, this tiny magazine is an all time favorite among Children's of all age.

Grihalakshmi (Women's Publication): An exclusive magazine for women of Kerala, Grihalakshmi, was launched in the year 1979. It is a comprehensive magazine covering all aspects of feminine psyche.

Thozhilvartha (Opportunities Publication): The first employment paper in Malayalam, Thozhilvartha was an intent triumph among the youths of Kerala. Reporting almost every employment opportunities in Kerala, the paper proves to be an alternative for the state's informative cell in service sector.

Arogyamasika (Health Publication): Arogyamasika is monthly magazine and publishing in Malayalam language, Kerala. It first printed in the year 1997. It is focusing mainly on health related features; maintain body fitness tips, yoga, and concentration on mental and physical energy.

Sports Magazine (Sports Publication in Malayalam): A complete monthly for the sports lovers of Kerala, Mathrubhumi sports magazine was launched on 5th June 1994. It is greatly contributed for providing an insight into the national and international sports events.

Yathra (Travel Magazine): 1st published in 2008, Mathrubhumi Yathra is devoted to travelers. The contents are of vivid itineraries, travelogues, location details, routes and maps, geographical histories and cuisines. The magazine is now popular and aptly enriched with colorful photographs and travel guidelines.

Minnaminni (For Pre-Primary/ Lower Primary Kids): It was launched in November 2010.

Mathrubhumi Azhchapathippu (Illustrated Weekly): Launched on 18th of January 1932, Mathrubhumi Illustrated weekly is the number one literary weekly in Malayalam.

Star & Style: Mathrubhumi Star & Style was released on 11th April 2013 at a function held at Le Meriden on Wednesday. It is a new publication from Mathrubhumi catering to the film world. The magazine is “vishukaineettam” from Mathrubhumi to Malayalees on its 90th birth anniversary. The stars from the film world led by Mammooty and Mohanlal, prominent personalities from industries, commercial and political sector, attended the function.

Competitors:

Malayala Manorama: is a daily newspaper in Malayalam language published in the state of Kerala; it was first published as a weekly on 14th march 1890, and currently has a readership over 16 million. The Week is an Indian weekly is also brought out by the Manorama group. Malayala Manorama has 32 publications all over India in 5 languages (English, Hindi, Malayalam, Tamil and Bengali)

Deshabhimani: this is a Malayalam newspaper run by Communist Party of India (Marxist). It started as a weekly in 1942 and converted to a daily in 1946. Deshabhimani has 6 different editions located at Kozhikode, Trivandrum, Kannur, Kottayam, Kochi and Thrissur.

Kerala Kaumudi: It is a popular Malayalam newspaper found in 1911. It publishes from Trivandrum, Kollam, Alappuzha, Kochi, Kozhikode, and Kannur in Kerala and Bangalore.

Deepika: It is one of the oldest newspapers publishes in India. The first issue came out on April 15th.

Mangalam: Launched kottayam edition of the daily on 16th of March 1989.

3. Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the recruitment and selection procedure followed by Mathrubhumi Printing and Publishing Co. Ltd
- ✓ To understand actual selection methods followed by the company
- ✓ To know the company's effectiveness of the present recruitment strategy.
- ✓ To understand whether the employees are satisfied with the recruitment and selection procedure and whether it leads to engagement

Primary data for this study was collected through:

- ✓ **Observation:** observation method involves recording the behavior patterns of the respondents without communicating with them. In this study, a direct

observation of the recruitment and selection employees in company was observed.

- ✓ **Questionnaire:** A questionnaire consists of 18 number of questions printed in a definite order on a form or set of forms. The questionnaire is directly given to the respondents. Sample size of 50 respondents

Discussion:

Table 1: Data pertaining to how the employees are recruited

S.No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Internal Recruitment (promotion, employee referral etc.)	7	14
2	External Recruitment (Advertisement, Consultancies, Campus etc)	18	36
3	Both	25	50
	Total	50	100

The Above table shows both external and internal methods are used for recruitment. External methods seem to be having more preference in the company.

Figure 1: Data pertaining to the recruitment and selection method preferred by the company

As the company is a News paper company, Mathrubhumi Printing and Publishing Co.Ltd prefer Advertising method mostly. Advertisement can help them to find as many applicants as possible to apply for the job and for the company, advertising is less expensive and it has wide reach.

Figure 2: Data pertaining to the kind of interview used for selection by the Company

From the above data, it is evident that the company is giving more importance to preliminary interview and discussion interview

The above data is clearly shows the satisfaction level of employees on recruitment procedure through which they are selected. The 20 % of the respondents are says that they are dissatisfied while 80 % of the respondents says that are satisfied with the recruitment procedure through which they are selected. The study shows that there is a positive relationship between selection and recruitment methods with employee engagement

4. Conclusion:

This study has focused on the recruitment and selection process at Mathrubhumi Printing and Publishing Co. Ltd, Calicut. *Mathrubhumi*, the second largest Malayalam daily, has an impeccable nationalist origin. Based in Calicut, *Mathrubhumi* was founded in 1922 as a public limited company in the aftermath of Gandhi's non-cooperation movement. Recruitment is the process of by which organizations locate and attract individuals to fill job vacancies. Recruitment in the Mathrurubhumi Printing and Publishing Co. Ltd follows HR Planning and goes in hand in hand with selection process by which organizations evaluate the suitability of the candidates. The project contains information about what is recruitment and selection, its definition, process of recruitment and selection at mathrubhumi Printing and Publishing Co.Ltd. This study revealed more the practical exposure of recruitment and selection process. It can be clearly concluded that for a company to succeed all it takes is the proper recruitment and selection strategies which also shapes the overall manpower management of the company. Mathrubhumi Printing and Publishing Co. Ltd is a reputed company with 100 years of experience. Therefore the company has an effective system of recruitment and selection which leads to employee engagement

5. References:

1. Ashwathappa K, "Human Resource Management" , Tata McGrawhill : New Delhi, 2009
2. Batra and Dangwal, "Human Resource Management", Develop Publication Private Ltd.: New Delhi, 2009.
3. C.B Mamoria and S.V Gankar "Personnel Management Text and Cases", Himalaya Publishing House: Mumbai, 2001.
4. Decenzo Robins, "Personnel/ Human Resource Management", Third edition, Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi, 2006.
5. Eric Garner, "Recruitment and Selection: Hiring People You Want" Eric Garner and Ventus Publishing Aps, 2012.
6. Gary Dessler "Human Resource Management", 2nd Edition, Excel Books: New Delhi, 2006.

7. Kothari C. R "Research Methodology Methods and Techniques", New Age Publication: New Delhi, 2009.
8. Tapomy Deb "Strategic Approach to HRM: Concept, Tools and Application", Atlantic Publishers and Distributers: New Delhi, 2006.
9. Barney, J. B., and P. M. Wright. "On Becoming a Strategic Partner: The Role of Human Resources in Gaining Competitive Advantage." *Human Resource Management* 37.1 (1998): 31-46.
10. Roos, Johann and von Krogh, Georg, *Organizational Epistemology* (New York, NY: Macmillan, 1995).
11. Russ, Gail S., "Cultural Knowledge in Organizations: Exploring the Collective Mind," *Personnel Psychology* 46:2 (Summer 1993): 395-398.
12. Ryan, Margaret, "Human Resource Management and the Politics of Knowledge," *Leadership and Organization Development Journal* 16:5 (1995): 3-10.
13. Sackmann, Sonja A., "Culture and Subcultures: An Analysis of Organizational Knowledge," *Administrative Science Quarterly* 37:1 (March 1992): 140-161.
14. Scultz, Theodore, *Investing in People* (Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 1974).
15. Wright, P. M., and G. C. McMahan. "Theoretical Perspectives for Strategic Human Resource Management." *Journal of Management* 18.2 (1992): 295-320.